

Exploring Higher Education Internationalization in Oman: Academic staff perspectives

Saud Albusaidi

Aaisha Albusaidi

1. Introduction

The concept of inclusion in internationalization goes beyond simple numerical representation and necessitates a revolutionary strategy which actively dismantles institutional obstacles. According to UNESCO (2021, cited in Undie et al., 2025), internationalization encourages variety by integrating global perspectives and increasing access to people from various socioeconomic and ethnic origins. Inclusion is described as ‘the culture of positive behaviours that create professional and personal environments where individuals have the opportunity and support to achieve their personal and professional ambitions’ (Undie et al., 2025, p.130). Inclusion can be understood as the process to which those who are historically or generally outside of the majority are made to feel they are part of the organization or system. This does not always suggest the system has completely changed, but it does note that the structure has identified those who are less represented as being integral to the organization, or in this case, the university. Internationalization of higher education (HE) is defined as ‘the variety of policies and programmes that universities and governments implement in response to globalization’ (Kufaine, 2024, p.1030). Within this dynamic, internationalization has the potential to enhance cross-cultural understanding, leverage diverse perspectives, and create opportunities for global engagement and contribution (Undie et al., 2025). This potential is evident beyond Western contexts, as seen in Oman (Al’Abri et al., 2022; Albusaidi, 2022a, 2022b) and Seychelles (Hardy, 2021). Researchers in the Omani context found that the internationalization process has impacted academic programs, research, and services, such as quality assurance (Albusaidi, 2022b; Hubais and Muftahu, 2022). However, there exists the potential to create certain tensions and challenges due to political, cultural, and linguistic factors, as well as values and beliefs, which are often overlooked. This research aims to fill this gap by exploring these tensions from the perspective of staff working at English Language Centres (ELCs), thereby providing a unique contribution to the literature. In addition, the lack of an internationalization policy and strategy in the HE system in Oman leads to ad hoc practices, which eventually hinder the overall progress of the internationalization process (Albusaidi, 2022a, 2022b; Al Harthy, 2011; Al-Lamki, 2006). Moreover, different cultural and linguistic values from the West, where the internationalization phenomenon begins, may reveal various and even divergent interpretations on integrating diverse cultures and languages in the HE community (Al Abry, 2018; Marginson, 2014), which is another

overlooked area, particularly in Omani higher education institutions (HEIs). By challenging existing narratives predominantly framed by Western contexts, the aim of this research is to provide comparative insights with other regional or international contexts. While this may be challenging due to the limited available literature in Oman, the goal is to articulate future contributions to global HE internationalization practices.

1.1. Context

Oman offers a unique context for exploring HE internationalization precisely because of its linguistic landscape. While Arabic is the official language and Islam is its religion, English has a distinctive position as a foreign language (Al-Issa and Al-Bulushi, 2012). This linguistic dynamic creates an intriguing setting for examining how a traditionally Arabic-speaking nation navigates international educational approaches through a non-native language medium. The current study was conducted in an Omani university, which was given the pseudonym 'Gulf University' for ethical purposes. At this university, English is the medium of instruction in all units except for Arabic language and history courses, which are taught in Arabic. The university offers diplomas, higher diplomas, and bachelor's degrees in business, information technology (IT), engineering, and pharmacy. The university has 131 international students, which represents 0.39% of the total student body. At the same time, as of 2019, approximately 2152 non-Omani academic staff are employed at the university. This includes individuals from countries such as the UK, the USA, Canada, Australia, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, the Philippines, Syria, Egypt, and Sudan. The ELC offers courses in English, mathematics, and computer skills. The roles of the ELC are to prepare students with adequate English language skills for their undergraduate level, promote their knowledge of a co-educational environment, expose them to staff from different cultures, and enhance their intercultural competencies and lifelong learning (Albusaidi, 2024).

The discussion above underscores how complex it is to incorporate different linguistic and cultural norms into Omani HE. Potential cultural conflicts in the internationalization process, especially within the ELCs, are anticipated due to the small number of international students despite the presence of a sizable and diverse staff. By concentrating on these dynamics, the study hopes to provide insightful information about the tensions and opportunities for internationalization in Omani HE, contributing to broader academic discussions.

1.2. Aims and research questions

The current study explores local and international staff perspectives and attitudes towards internationalization practices and activities related to students, staff, and the curriculum in a university in Oman. Consequently, it addresses the following questions:

- 1. How do academic staff at the Gulf University in Oman perceive internationalization that relates to students, staff, and the curriculum?*
- 2. How do the perspectives of academic staff at the Gulf University towards internationalization compare across ethnicity, place of qualification, and gender?*

2. Review of the literature

One response to globalization is internationalization. The former can be defined as ‘the economic, political, and societal forces pushing... higher education toward greater international involvement’ (Altbach and Knight, 2007, p.290), whereas the response to these forces or dimensions is ‘internationalization’.

2.1. Rationales of internationalization

Scholars in internationalization research traditionally categorize motivations for international engagement into four distinct domains: academic/educational, cultural/social, political, and economic (de Wit, 2002; Knight and de Wit, 1995). The academic rationale refers to the aim and function of the institution in terms of the ideas, knowledge, and values which are exchanged at the national and international levels (Knight, 2013). This is also done through promoting global awareness and a deeper involvement of learners with global issues (Seeber et al., 2016). The cultural rationale refers to fostering mutual intercultural understandings and national cultural identity. This aims to enable individuals to learn skills that equip them to be global citizens. The political rationale of internationalization, similarly, refers to the country’s role and position. Such motivation can emerge through ‘national security, stability, national and regional identity, as well as ideological influences’ (de Wit, 2002, p.86). The economic rationale refers to the income of the institution (commercial) or through developing a knowledge economy.

2.2. Approaches to internationalization

The literature presents a framework consisting of six approaches for analysing the development and implementation of internationalization in HE contexts (de Wit, 2002; Knight, 2004; Knight and de Wit, 1995). Firstly, the activity approach describes internationalization as various types of activities and programmes, including the recruitment of international staff and students, academic mobility and joint research. Secondly, the outcome approach is about ‘education where quality is thought of in terms of knowledge, skills, interests, values, and attitudes of the students’ (Knight, 1999, p.15), in which the outcome is the focus. Thirdly, the rationale approach is illustrated in terms of the importance of internationalizing national education, where the focus on political and economic

rationales has become the key. Then there is the ‘at home’ approach, which describes the culture of the institution, where international and intercultural perspectives and values are established and promoted at the home campus. In contrast, the ‘abroad’ approach describes the cross-country delivery of education through different means, such as e-learning. Finally, the process approach describes the academic activities, organizational policies and procedures of the organization.

Overall, these approaches are interrelated because some internationalization aspects and practices can fall within different approaches. The research at hand is not positioned within any one approach but utilizes this framework to explore the staff perspectives in an Omani HEI on internationalization aspects that relate to students, staff and the curriculum.

2.3. de Wit’s model of internationalization

The version of the internationalization circle that was modified by de Wit (2002) shows nine key components of implementing an internationalization strategy, as the following diagram illustrates.

Figure 1: The internationalization circle
(Source: de Wit 2002, p.136)

The first phase of implementing internationalization is analysing the context, where internal and external factors are assessed for their influence on the institution's capacity for internationalization. This involves examining the goals, policies, and the broader socio-

economic and cultural environment, providing a solid foundation for the internationalization process (LeBeau, 2018). The second phase involves awareness or needs analysis, focusing on understanding the benefits of internationalization for various stakeholders, such as students, staff, and the community. This awareness is vital for gathering support and commitment across the institution. The third phase is planning, which involves identifying objectives, priorities, and strategies for internationalization. This can include outlining academic activities, events, and services that will support the internationalization efforts.

The following phases are implementation and operationalization, which involve putting strategies into action. This requires coordination across departments and/or branches to ensure that resources are allocated efficiently and effectively to support any internationalization initiatives. The review phase is sometimes overlooked (LeBeau, 2018), but its importance lies in evaluating the effectiveness of the internationalization efforts against the initial goals and objectives set during the planning phase.

Phase eight is reinforcement, where successful strategies are reinforced, and adjustments are made as necessary. This phase also involves developing incentives and recognition for participants (LeBeau, 2018) to ensure that the internationalization process is dynamic, resilient, and adaptable to changing circumstances. The final phase focuses on the integration effect, where internationalization is incorporated into the broader institutional framework to ensure it becomes a sustainable part of the institution's culture and practices. This is crucial for institutionalizing internationalization within the system rather than maintaining it as a separate strategy (LeBeau, 2018).

Within the research, this cycle provides a clear and comprehensive framework for understanding the complex process of internationalization in HE. It helps clarify the stages involved and their interconnectivity. Additionally, it contributes to the theoretical understanding of internationalization, allowing for a deeper analysis of how and where institutions fit into the internationalization process, which offers a structured way to analyse internationalization in Oman.

2.4. Variables affecting staff perspectives

The current study conducts a comparative analysis of the results of a questionnaire focusing on three variables in the respondent metadata: ethnicity (Arab vs. non-Arab), educational background (local vs. abroad), and gender. The first is ethnic grouping, where the participants are divided into two groups: Arabs and non-Arabs. These two divisions were made due to language, culture, and religion. Research shows that a person's language influences how they view themselves and how others view them (Sysoyev, 2002). Additionally, when individuals master additional languages, they can develop better international understanding and intercultural skills (Saunders and Fisher, 2020). Cultural background shapes how individuals

interpret and understand international cultural practices (McDermott-Levy, 2011). Similarly, religious beliefs contribute to an individual's self-identity and influence how they interpret others' cultural practices (Ramadan, 2017). Therefore, language, culture, and religion are expected to play a role in shaping Arab participants' perspectives in this study.

The second variable is completing a qualification abroad. The survey asked the participants to indicate whether they had completed a qualification abroad or not. The literature shows that completing a qualification abroad can offer a range of qualities, values, experiences, and skills to students (Behrnd and Porzelt, 2012; Gong et al., 2021; McDermott-Levy, 2011; Sung, 2019; Wang, 2018; Wang et al., 2019). In Turkey, it was found that learners who studied abroad gained new competencies and skills and broadened their worldview, which led them to be more open to and appreciative of cultural and religious diversity (Erden, 2013; Karakaş, 2020).

The final variable considered was gender. Researchers found that gender differences occur in social interactions and interpersonal styles in mixed-gender groups (Carli, 1990, 2009), which is expected to shape cultural understandings. Females in some Arab contexts, such as Oman (McDermott-Levy, 2011), may not have equal opportunities or the liberty to interact or engage with male colleagues or international peers due to traditions and cultural norms (McDermott-Levy, 2011). Females, moreover, may have less trust in their foreign colleagues and may not share some experiences with them (Yuden et al., 2020). These findings suggest that gender characteristics are likely to be transferred into differences in attitudes between males and females towards internationalization activities and practices.

3. Methodology

The study employed a mixed-methods approach to investigate English language staff perspectives at a selected university in Oman. Guided by a pragmatic philosophical paradigm which emphasizes practical implications and real-world applications, the investigation selected methods and procedures based on their usefulness in answering research questions, aiming to produce practical results and actionable information (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). An exploratory sequential design was implemented across four stages to address the research questions, as the following diagram shows:

Figure 2: Four stages of the exploratory sequential design
(Source: Subedi, 2016, p.573)

The research was conducted at an Omani public university. The data collection process consisted of two primary phases, beginning with qualitative data collection through ten semi-structured interviews with academic staff from four different nationalities (see Appendix 1).

Table 1: Key information about interviewees with pseudonyms

	Pseudonyms	Gender	Nationality	Number of years working at this university
1	Tara	Female	British	5
2	Lema	Female	Indian	11
3	Idrees	Male	Indian	8
4	Bayan	Female	Indian	7
5	Ali	Male	Indian	8
6	Salim	Male	Syrian	6
7	Younis	Male	Omani	10
8	Tahani	Female	Omani	9
9	Ahmed	Male	Omani	7
10	Salma	Female	Omani	11

The participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure a balanced representation of local and international academic staff, reflecting diverse perspectives. An official email was sent to the heads of ELCs, who then forwarded it to their staff. Staff members were kindly requested to register their names via a link included in the email, which was exclusively accessible to the researchers. This approach was employed to maintain participant confidentiality, ensuring they would remain anonymous to the heads of the ELCs. The interviews were conducted to gather in-depth insights into the research questions; hence, each interview took from 30 to 50 minutes. The interview data was analysed using NVivo software for thematic analysis, which facilitated the systematic generation of codes and themes.

Following the qualitative phase, and based on the themes identified, a survey instrument was developed and distributed to all 563 academic staff members. The survey was designed to quantify the qualitative findings and reach a broader audience within the institution. The quantitative data was analysed using SPSS software, incorporating both descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic characteristics and inferential statistics. The demographic offers an essential context to understand the participant population and the relevant trends. For the inferential, using Chi-square, Mann-Whitney (MW-U), and Fisher's Exact tests (FET) helped examine relationships between the three variables discussed earlier. The Chi-square was employed to determine whether a significant association exists between categorical variables. This offers insights into the independence of these variables within the sample. MW-U was run to compare the differences between two independent groups as the data did

not meet the assumptions of normality. FET was implemented as the sample sizes were small; thus, it ensured accurate results when examining associations. Finally, Kendall's tau-b was also run to analyse the strength of the association and report the effect size.

The study focused on three key variables: ethnicity (Arabs and non-Arabs), place of qualification (domestic and international), and gender (males and females). From a total population of 563 academic staff, 148 participants (26.2% response rate) engaged in the study following the distribution of three reminders. The participants represented 21 different nationalities, with 32.4% being Arab and 67.6% non-Arab. The staff members who completed a qualification abroad represented 52.7%, compared to 47.3% who completed their qualifications in their home country. The gender distribution was 44.6% male and 55.4% female.

Data triangulation was achieved through the integration of both qualitative and quantitative findings, enhancing the validity and reliability of the results. This methodological approach allowed for a comprehensive examination of the research questions while providing both depth through qualitative insights and breadth through quantitative data.

Ethics were taken into consideration prior to data collection. First, approval was obtained from the university headquarters where this study was conducted. A letter was provided to the heads of the ELCs while introducing the aims and objectives of the study. Each participant received a copy of the participant information sheet, which explained the privacy of the data, anonymity, the risks of participation, why they were selected, and how the data would be used. The interviewees were also asked before the interview if they had any questions and if they wished to withdraw at any time, as well as the procedure for addressing issues and seeking clarification. Pseudonyms were used before transcribing the interviews and when reporting the findings. For the survey, an email was sent with a consent form, which respondents needed to agree to before responding. Emails were not collected prior to answering the questions; however, the survey link was shared by the heads of the ELCs.

4. Results and findings

This section integrates the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study, addressing the research questions and aims. Although the quantitative and qualitative data were collected separately, they are now integrated in this section to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic and to avoid repetition, thereby strengthening the conclusions drawn. The findings are organized around three key areas of internationalization – students, staff, and curriculum – which were the focus of the study. The first theme sheds light on the perspectives of academic staff regarding international students and highlights the

participants' limited awareness of potential challenges. Theme two presents staff views regarding international staff and also indicates their constrained understanding of internationalization. Theme three sheds light on staff perspectives on curriculum internationalization, which were shaped by balancing international cultural considerations and local values. Each theme integrates both quantitative data and qualitative insights to provide a fuller picture of the issues discussed.

4.1. Perceived benefits of international students and awareness of potential challenges

Recruiting international students is a key aspect of HE internationalization. HEIs worldwide have prioritized it in their strategic plans and policy documents, providing facilities and opportunities to recruit international students (Heng, 2017; Jones, 2017; Singh, 2019). Figure 3 found that over three-quarters (88.5%, 131 out of 148) of those who responded agreed or strongly agreed that students from overseas assist local students in improving their English language skills. The implication is that staff members view internationalization as an opportunity for local students to develop their English language skills.

Figure 3: Responses to the statement 'International students can help local students in improving their English language skills'

The interviews illuminated participants' expectations of how the presence of international students can affect local students' use of the target language without considering the potential barriers or tensions. For example, three participants viewed internationalization as boosting the use of English among students (Tahani, Salim and Ali, interviews). They argued that when foreign and Omani students studied together, English language would be the dominant

medium of communication. Furthermore, one participant, Ali, criticized the monoculture (Omani exclusively) of learners since it limited their usage of the target language. Only by recruiting students from other nationalities would the university be able to initiate a *'shift in the culture'* which would encourage *'local students'* to improve their proficiency in English (Tahani, interview). This proposes that the presence of students from overseas is a vital part of learning in a diverse context, where social and linguistic interactions can occur, which aligns with those of Heng (2017), Jones (2017), and Singh (2019). However, a one-way benefit which does not consider the potential mutual benefits for international students emerged from the interviews, which may explain the current low number of international students in these ELCs.

Another anticipated possible impact of internationalization was its ability to increase local students' abilities. Two participants said that foreign and Omani students studying together would improve *'local students'* cognitive skills, language skills (Lema, interview), life skills, technical skills, and job skills (Tahani, interview), consequently improving their intercultural skills. Furthermore, Figure 4 shows that more than three-quarters (82.5%, 122 out of 148) of survey participants agreed or strongly agreed that enrolling of students from overseas helps local students improve their cognitive skills. On one hand, this suggests that international student interactions create a rich, transformative learning environment that goes beyond traditional classroom boundaries. On the other hand, the agreement, and the emphasis on aiding local students, suggest a one-way benefit, as foreign students were thought of as improving the cognitive skills of local students rather than shared benefits between local and international students.

Figure 4: Responses to the statement *'Recruiting international students helps local students enhance their cognitive skills'*

Another interpretation of internationalization was the perception that introducing international students would motivate ‘*Omani students*’ to work harder and, ultimately, improve their competency level and grades (Younis, interview). Indeed, the survey data revealed that more than three-quarters (83.1%, 123 out of 148) of respondents agreed/strongly agreed that recruiting international students enhances the motivation of local students, as illustrated in Figure 5. This underscores a complex psychological dynamic in educational internationalization, suggesting that cross-cultural student interactions create a competitive yet collaborative learning environment that stimulates academic engagement.

Figure 5: Responses to the statement ‘*Recruiting international students enhances the motivation of local students*’

The significant gap between those who agree and disagree suggests that the presence of international students enables local students to become more motivated. The findings, also, provided empirical evidence of a one-way benefit of internationalization, and indicated a possible lack of awareness among participants of challenges faced in classrooms with local and international students, which were identified in another context by Sawir (2011) and Sawir et al. (2008). The current findings, which showed no discernible variations, imply that participants did not completely grasp the intricate dynamics at play and the potential tensions associated with this internationalization process.

In summary, this section revealed that most staff at this Omani university felt that the presence of international students could bring potential benefits to local students. Staff members, however, were mainly unaware of the true difficulties in putting internationalization into practice. For instance, they failed to consider the fact that the presence of foreign students does not always result in improved target language proficiency and learning experiences

(Otten, 2003; Teekens, 2003). The data mainly suggest a one-way benefit in terms of how internationalization can only benefit local students rather than mutual benefits between local and international students. In Australia, it was also found that ‘there is very little reciprocity in community benefits that are returned to the international students. International students often meet more hardships than favors, specifically regarding issues with employment, accommodation, exploitation, discrimination, and cultural segregation’ (Marangell et al., 2018, p.1446). The perspectives of Younis, Ali, Salim, Tahani, and Lema illustrate that there are no significant differences among Arab and non-Arab staff, staff with domestic and international qualifications. In addition, there is a belief among both the male and female staff that recruiting international students in these ELCs enhances local students' English proficiency, cognitive skills, motivation, and cultural understanding. Consequently, while internationalization was viewed primarily as a unilateral advantage and the associated challenges were not thoroughly considered, it illustrates the present situation characterized by a limited number of international students and indicates the absence of mutuality in these ELCs.

4.2. Perceived benefits of international staff with a limited view of internationalization

Two sub-themes emerged from the qualitative data as a result of the participants' varied interpretations of internationalization in relation to hiring and integrating foreign employees. The impact of foreign employees on campus culture is the subject of the first sub-theme. Here, the participants defined internationalization as 1) introducing cultural values to local staff and students, 2) exchanging experiences and knowledge, and 3) improving non-native staff members' English language proficiency. This sub-theme draws attention to tensions and challenges which may emerge when putting internationalization into practice because of regional cultural and religious beliefs.

The second sub-theme posits that staff development and professional development programmes are essential for enhancing the quality of education within the framework of HE internationalization (Jeannin, 2016; Leask, 2001, 2004; Luxon and Peelo, 2009; Svetlik and Braček-Lalić, 2016). The significance of these programmes in improving the quality of both domestic and foreign employees was highlighted by the participants. The results, however, draw attention to tensions that may arise during the execution of this attempt to internationalize.

4.2.1. Effects of the presence of international staff on the on-campus culture

Two participants perceived internationalization in terms of international staff not only adding values, skills, and knowledge to the local culture and students but ‘*transferring a whole culture*’, as explained by Tahani, an Omani staff member. Another Omani participant (Salma,

interview) also expressed a cautious view regarding an international staff member who strived to present their religion positively to students and some staff. Salma implied that some students are more easily influenced, which may lead them to abandon their religious roots. These viewpoints might be interpreted as a barrier to internationalization and draw attention to a significant worry voiced by local employees regarding potential conflicts regarding the workplace and cultural norms as it relates to internationalization. These two local participants felt that what international staff bring to this local environment was not necessarily positive. Although internationalization aimed to *'transfer... a whole culture'* (Tahani, interview), this local context does not intuitively accept it at face value but reconstructs it according to the guidelines of the local religion and culture. Additionally, Tahani felt that her own culture – Omani or Arab culture in general – had less of an impact than the dominant culture that the international staff brought to the local setting. As a result, she is unsure of how it could improve the cultural awareness of international staff.

Additionally, Salma perceived internationalization as *'knowing another culture, different ways of thinking, having different perspectives'*, which resonates with the new ways of thinking that are highlighted by Altbach (2013) and Patil-Vishwanath and Mummery (2019) within the context of homogenization. Salma acknowledges that exposure to diverse perspectives could enhance her understanding and help her be more open-minded, which can facilitate the ability to switch between different ideas and see things from various perspectives (Benet-Martínez et al., 2006; Patil-Vishwanath and Mummery, 2019). She stated that she could see the world in different ways due to her interaction with international staff and felt this was positive. However, she did not comment on the 'ways of thinking' and 'different perspectives' acquired from her local culture, nor on how they differ from those of others or international ways of thinking.

Five participants (Ali, Ahmed, Salim, Younis, and Tahani) perceived internationalization in terms of staff members exchanging information and experiences. Significantly, the findings show that nearly all survey participants (95.2%, 141 out of 148) agreed or strongly agreed that sharing experiences with staff from other nationalities facilitates communication (see Figure 6). This illuminates a critical, often overlooked dimension of internationalization, suggesting that staff from different countries share their knowledge and experiences and learn from each other; hence, it is not solely about recruiting international staff but also about sharing knowledge and experiences.

Figure 6: Responses to the statement ‘Working with staff from different countries helps share their experiences with each other’

The qualitative data suggests that Arab and non-Arab participants were driven by the belief that working with staff from different countries has several benefits such as learning from one another (Ahmed and Salim, interview), exchanging experiences (Ahmed and Younis, interview), sharing cultural aspects and values (Tahani, interview), and disseminating knowledge (Ali and Younis, interview). These appear to be benefits that these participants not only currently lack but actively desire and value in their professional environment. Although knowledge-sharing is a key principle of internationalization, three Arab participants perceived it as limited to what was acceptable to local cultural and religious values because staff *‘should not go beyond the scope of the religion and the culture’* (Tara, interview). Such concerns were not discussed by non-Arab participants, implying that Arab participants' cultural and religious values may have influenced their views on this dimension and acted as important parameters for knowledge-sharing in this context. This could be attributed to *‘conservatism in the country’* (Bayan, interview), referring to the context's historically conservative social and cultural standards. As a result, the fact that the educational system, in Oman and many other countries, was established on local cultural and religious values means that staff perceptions will reflect this. Although this tension can create a challenge, five Muslim Arab participants (Ahmed, Salim, Younis, Tara and Tahani) suggested that internationalization can be implemented in line with the cultural and religious values of the homeland.

When examining staff perspectives on whether working with colleagues from different countries helps them share experiences, the analysis revealed some interesting patterns. Table 2 demonstrates that non-Arab staff (mean rank = 79.18) showed significantly more positive

views about cross-cultural experience sharing compared to Arab staff (mean rank = 64.76). However, when participants who responded 'neither agree nor disagree' were excluded from the analysis, this difference disappeared, indicating that the initial difference was primarily driven by neutral responses rather than clear disagreement. This finding aligns with interview data where Arab staff expressed interest in international collaboration, but with an important proviso – they preferred such exchanges to occur within the framework of local cultural norms.

Regarding qualifications, Table 2 shows there were no significant differences between staff who completed qualifications abroad and those who did not. Similarly, gender did not play a significant role in how staff viewed international collaboration. These findings suggest a more nuanced picture: while initial quantitative results suggested that cultural background influenced staff perspectives on international collaboration, deeper analysis revealed that Arab staff are not opposed to international collaboration, but rather seek such exchanges within culturally appropriate parameters. Educational background and gender do not appear to shape these views in meaningful ways.

Table 2: MW-U for 'In my ELC, working with staff from different countries helps them share experiences with each other'

Item	Dependent variables	Independent variables	n	Mean rank	U	Z	MW-U p-value	Kendall's Correlations		
								Tau-b	P-value	
5	In my ELC, working with staff from different countries helps them share experiences with each other.	Ethnicity	Arab	48	64.76	1932.500	2.183	.029 *	.176	.029 *
			Non-Arab	100	79.18					
		Qualification	Completed a qualification abroad	78	75.97	2615.500	.501	.636	-.040	.616
			Did not complete a qualification abroad	70	72.86					
		Gender	Male	66	76.06	2603.00	.453	.662	-.037	.651
			Female	82	73.24					

Note: * $p < .05$

4.2.2. Internationalization interpreted as the need for staff development

As a key to successfully and efficiently implementing internationalization activities, two participants in the current study defined internationalization as providing staff with contemporary approaches and strategies to improve their teaching (Salim and Bayan, interview). This offers insight into how an Omani institution hopes to apply internationalization concepts to become part of the global knowledge economy. This ensures that local staff can access best practices in the field while continuously refining their own notions and ideas.

For example, Bayan, an international staff member, understood internationalization to mean that instructors need to be highly prepared and competent in order to teach and prepare students to meet international standards. She added that teachers should take the initiative in learning by *'take(ing) up professional development courses'* to enhance their knowledge and skills for the benefit of the student community (Bayan, interview). Bayan argued that staff should develop themselves through *'professional development courses'* and engaging in ELC *'initiatives'*. She was driven by various local and global situations in which instructors were asked to participate in professional development courses and assist in planning and delivering programmes (Leask, 2001). Bayan also commented that *'professional development courses... are required to compete globally'*, indicating that such courses provide teachers with skills and knowledge that could assist them in this regard. This could attract international staff to join this institution, which is a strategy for brain gain. To promote internationalization, she argued that such programmes should equip staff with *'various trending issues and the... latest developments in our field that are happening globally'* (Bayan, interview). She stated that conferences, workshops, and on-campus programmes allow staff to gather weekly to discuss subjects, exchange experiences, and share viewpoints. Bayan was also inspired by the local context as she considered how professional development initiatives benefited staff at her ELC.

Furthermore, Figure 7 shows that the majority of staff (89.8%, 133 out of 148) agree or strongly agree that they participate in professional development programmes that engage them with current topics in their ELCs. Only a small percentage (4.1%, 6 out of 148) disagree or strongly disagree. Similarly, as illustrated in Figure 8, more than three-quarters of respondents (81.8%, 121 out of 148) agree or strongly agree that staff members attend international academic activities, such as conferences, with only 4.8% (7 out of 148) disagreeing. These findings suggest that staff view such initiatives not simply as administrative requirements but as valuable strategic opportunities for intellectual growth, cross-cultural understanding, and institutional transformation. This aligns with the central research question, which examines how staff perceive internationalization activities, showing that many staff members actively engage in professional development and international academic events, seeing them as integral to enhancing their academic and professional experiences.

Figure 7: Responses to the statement 'Staff are involved in professional development programmes that engage them in learning about various trending issues'

Figure 8: Responses to the statement 'Staff participate in international academic events, such as conferences'

An MW-U test was then used to determine whether this agreement (81.8%, 121 out of 148) varied by major contextual variables. Analysis of staff participation in international academic events revealed significant differences between cultural groups. Non-Arab staff reported

notably higher levels of participation (mean rank = 80.94) compared to their Arab colleagues (mean rank = 61.07), with this difference being statistically significant ($p = .003$), as shown in Table 3. This pattern aligns with previous research in Oman by Al-Ghatrifi (2016), who identified several factors affecting Arab staff participation, including lower motivation levels, limited awareness of conference benefits, and reduced involvement in local development programmes that could encourage international engagement.

The gap between Arab and non-Arab staff participation showed a moderate association ($\tau_b = .227$, $p = .004$), suggesting that cultural background plays a meaningful role in how staff members engage with international academic events (see Table 3). This finding points to potential areas for institutional intervention, particularly in addressing the specific needs and concerns of Arab staff regarding international academic participation.

Table 3: MW-U for ‘Staff participate in international academic events, such as conferences’

Item	Dependent variables	Independent variables	n	Mean rank	U	Z	MW-U p-value	Kendall's Correlations		
								Tau-b	P-value	
9	In my ELC, staff participate in international academic events, such as conferences.	Ethnicity	Arab	48	61.07	1755.500	2.918	.003 *	.227	.004 *
			Non-Arab	100	80.94					
		Qualification	Completed a qualification abroad	78	72.28	2557.000	.734	.464	.057	.463
			Did not complete a qualification abroad	70	76.97					
		Gender	Male	66	74.62	2698.000	.034	.974	-.003	.973
			Female	82	74.40					

Note: * $p < .05$

In addition, when examining how educational background intersects with ethnicity in relation to international academic participation, an interesting pattern emerged. According to Table 4, among staff who completed qualifications abroad, there was a significant association between ethnicity and views on international academic participation ($\tau_b = .255$, $p = .027$). This indicates that ethnic background significantly influences how these individuals perceive international engagement. However, for staff who completed their qualifications domestically, no significant relationship was found between ethnicity and participation views ($\tau_b = .052$, $p = .909$). The FET further supported these findings, showing no overall significant

association between ethnicity and participation for either group ($p = .052$ for those qualified abroad; $p = .552$ for those qualified domestically). Similarly, gender showed no significant relationship with participation views, regardless of whether staff obtained their qualifications abroad ($p = .430$) or domestically ($p = 1.000$). Overall, these results suggest that cultural background plays a more influential role in shaping views on international academic participation among staff with international educational experience, while such a relationship is largely absent for those who studied domestically.

Table 4: FET for ‘Staff participate in international academic events, such as conferences’

Item	DV (Row)	IV (Column)	IV (Layer) Completed a qualification abroad?	N of Valid Cases	Chi-square crosstab		Kendall’s association	
					Fisher’s value	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	tau-b	Exact Significance
9	In my ELC, staff participate in international academic events, such as conferences.	Ethnicity (Arab vs Non-Arab)	Yes	78	5.767	.052	.255	.027 *
			No	70	1.396	.552	.052	.909
		Gender (Male vs Female)	Yes	78	1.985	.430	.008	.982
			No	70	.467	1.000	.041	.912

Note: * $p < .05$

4.3. Perspectives on curriculum shaped by balancing international cultural considerations and local values

This section highlights the staff’s perceptions and interpretations of internationalization concerning their curriculum, encompassing curricular activities, content, and assessment (Jones and Killick, 2007). It centred on the perspectives of academic staff at this university in Oman regarding the incorporation of global cultural elements and topics. Participants viewed internationalization in the curriculum as involving global themes and issues in textbooks, as well as educating students about various cultures. However, these perceptions can cause disagreement within the local Omani context.

4.3.1. Inclusion of international cultural topics constrained by local values

Six of the local and international participants interpreted internationalization as including various cultural aspects, topics, and themes from around the globe in the textbooks (Younis, Tara, Baya, Ali, Tahani, and Idrees, interview). For example, an Omani participant, Younis,

asserted that the textbooks they used did not *'focus only on the Omani cultures'*. Rather, they covered *'different cultures'*. However, another Omani participant, Ahmed, who earned a qualification abroad, interpreted internationalization as embedding ideologies or orthodoxies from different cultures into the curriculum so that students would have *'a multi-dimensional... look at certain ideas instead of just having a local critical analysis of something'*. Ahmed might have been influenced by the notion of fostering critical thinking skills in students by encouraging them to assess different cultural concepts and practices and to reflect on how suitable these are for their local context (see Mok, 2007). In contrast, three Muslim Arab participants contended that the textbooks used in these ELCs contained ideas which were not acceptable in the local context (Tara, Salim and Ahmed, interview).

The results in Figure 9 indicate a significant disparity, with 83.1% (123 out of 148) agreeing or strongly agreeing that cultural diversity is acknowledged and integrated into the textbooks used in these ELCs. In contrast, only 5.4% (6 out of 148) disagreed, implying that these participants felt cultural diversity was inadequately represented in their textbooks, or they may have had differing expectations about what constitutes sufficient representation of various cultures. MW-U and FET were conducted to further explore this attitude.

Figure 9. Responses to the statement *'The textbooks teach students about different cultures worldwide'*

It was anticipated that Arab staff would hold different views on the subjects presented in the textbooks compared to non-Arab staff, mainly because most Arab interviewees in this study expressed a desire for themes and topics relevant to Arab countries and cultures to be included in their textbooks. The literature highlights a need for culturally sensitive and context-appropriate resources in classrooms for teaching English as a foreign language (Abd Rashid

and Ibrahim, 2018). Indeed, the results show clear differences in how Arab and non-Arab staff viewed the cultural content of ELC textbooks. Table 5 shows that Arab staff (mean rank = 62.59) were significantly less satisfied than non-Arab staff (mean rank = 80.22) with how the textbooks teach students about different cultures worldwide. This suggests that Arab staff members see limitations in how their cultural contexts are represented in these teaching materials.

There were no significant differences between staff who completed qualifications abroad and those who did not regarding their views on the textbooks' cultural content. Similarly, male and female staff members showed no significant differences in their perspectives on this issue.

Table 5: MW-U for ‘In my ELC, the textbooks teach students about different cultures worldwide’

Item	Dependent variables	Independent variables	n	Mean rank	U	Z	MW-U p-value	Kendall's Correlations		
								Tau-b	P-value	
10	In my ELC, the textbooks teach students about different cultures worldwide.	Ethnicity	Arab	48	62.59	1828.500	2.579	.010 *	.201	.010 *
			Non-Arab	100	80.22					
		Qualification	Completed a qualification abroad	78	71.73	2514.000	.914	.360	.071	.361
			Did not complete a qualification abroad	70	77.59					
		Gender	Male	66	79.77	2358.000	1.479	.141	-.115	.139
			Female	82	70.26					

Note: * $p < .05$

Additionally, the results in Figure 10 reveal that 31.76% (47 out of 148) neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement regarding the religious appropriateness of certain topics covered in the textbooks used in these ELCs. This reflects a degree of uncertainty surrounding the concept of ‘religious appropriateness’. However, nearly equal proportions of participants agreed (35.1%, 52 out of 148) and disagreed (33.1%, 49 out of 148) that the topics were religiously unsuitable. The statistically balanced responses about religious appropriateness suggest that religious sensitivity in educational content is a nuanced, context-dependent concept rather than a binary issue, but it also reflects the complex interplay between Islamic educational principles and contemporary content.

Figure 10. Responses to the statement 'Some of the topics the textbooks cover in these ELCs are not religiously appropriate for the Omani context'

The size of these groups – each comprising over a third of the respondents – indicates that this is a significant concern for the staff members. Several Islamic educators argue that introducing non-Islamic beliefs and perspectives to students may expose them to deviant ideas (Hamidaddin, 2019).

Religious appropriateness was also assessed using the MW-U test. Arab staff are generally more familiar with the religion of this context (Islam) (as noted by Tara, an Arab Muslim participant, in the interview) and may be more religious, but they might also be less sensitive to topics considered unethical (Muhamad, 2009). In Oman, several non-Arab staff come from Islamic backgrounds or are Muslims from Pakistan, India, and Malaysia. However, the results in Table 6 indicate that there was no significant difference between the two groups ($p = .918$, $n = 148$), and Kendall's tau-b showed a very weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.008$, $p = .918$). The results did reveal significant differences between those who obtained qualifications abroad and those who did not ($p = .028$, $n = 148$) with a weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.166$, $p = .028$). This suggests that studying abroad can broaden staff members' perspectives on religious values.

Table 6: MW-U for ‘Some of the topics that the textbooks cover in my ELC are not religiously appropriate to the Omani context’

Item	Dependent variables	Independent variables	n	Mean rank	U	Z	MW-U p-value	Kendall's Correlations		
								Tau-b	P-value	
12	Some of the topics that the textbooks cover in my ELC are not religiously appropriate to the Omani context.	Ethnicity	Arab	48	75.00	2376.000	.102	.918	-.008	.918
			Non-Arab	100	74.26					
		Qualification	Completed a qualification abroad	78	81.54	2181.000	2.198	.028*	-.166	.028*
			Did not complete a qualification abroad	70	66.66					
		Gender	Male	66	83.92	2084.000	2.501	.012*	-.189	.012*
			Female	82	66.91					

Note: * $p < .05$

Regarding gender, several Muslim male staff members identified concerns about inappropriate topics, while the literature claims that ‘women, at least in the West, are more religious than men’ (Woodhead, 2012, p.33). Nevertheless, the results showed significant differences in perspectives between male and female staff ($p = .012$, $n = 148$) with a weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.189$, $p = .012$). This finding supports the qualitative data indicating that male staff in this Omani context were more worried about the religious appropriateness of textbook topics than their female counterparts, which contradicts Woodhead’s (2012) assertion about women's religiosity in the West. Overall, the results indicate differing perspectives among respondents, influenced by gender and whether they had studied abroad.

When taking into account religious differences in curriculum design, over three-quarters of survey respondents (87.8%, 130 out of 148) agreed or strongly agreed that it is essential to consider these issues, as shown in Figure 11. In contrast, only 3.4% (5 out of 148) disagreed or strongly disagreed. While these results indicate a significant difference, the local context influences their views, as Oman is a Muslim country, leading to greater awareness and sensitivity to religious issues among educators (Al Sadi and Basit, 2013). Those who disagreed are likely to be less aware of the diverse religious beliefs and practices that are important in the Omani context.

Figure 11: Responses to the statement 'I feel when designing a curriculum, it is crucial to consider religious differences'

Table 7: MW-U for 'I feel when designing a curriculum, it is crucial to consider religious differences'

Item	Dependent variables	Independent variables	n	Mean rank	U	Z	MW-U p-value	Kendall's Correlations		
								Tau-b	P-value	
14	I feel when designing a curriculum, it is crucial to consider religious differences.	Ethnicity	Arab	48	86.18	1839.500	2.520	.012 *	-.199	.012*
			Non-Arab	100	68.90					
		Qualification	Completed a qualification abroad	78	74.81	2705.500	.103	.921	-.008	.918
			Did not complete a qualification abroad	70	74.15					
		Gender	Male	66	75.10	2666.500	.167	.872	-.013	.867
			Female	82	74.02					

Note: * $p < .05$

The results in Table 7 indicate significant differences between Arab and non-Arab perspectives ($p = .012$, $n = 148$), along with a weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.199$, $p = .012$).

This implies that Arab staff place greater importance on considering religious differences in curriculum design compared to their non-Arab counterparts. Conversely, non-Arab staff may prioritize presenting diverse religious values in the curriculum to encourage critical evaluation and discussions among students (Cheng and Beigi, 2012).

Regarding the influence of studying abroad on religious considerations in curriculum design, the results show no significant difference between those who obtained qualifications abroad and those who did not ($p = .921$, $n = 148$), along with a very weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.008$, $p = .918$). Additionally, no significant differences were found concerning gender ($p = .872$, $n = 148$), with a very weak negative association ($\tau_b = -.013$, $p = .867$). The fact that Arab staff, with a higher mean rank, agree that considering religious differences can enhance student learning indicates they view this consideration as important. However, this creates a tension that may hinder the implementation of internationalization principles by limiting exposure to diverse ideas. Despite some differences among the groups, there was a general consensus on the significance of religious considerations in curriculum design.

5. Discussion

This section presents the discussion of findings related to the research questions, particularly focusing on the perspectives of academic staff on internationalization at Gulf University in Oman. The discussion is organized around three main themes: perceived versus actual challenges of internationalization in this context, one-way versus mutual benefits of internationalization, and cultural barriers and local contextual challenges in implementing internationalization. Each theme explores the perceptions and tensions, and connects directly with the study's research questions, which examine perceptions of internationalization across students, staff, and the curriculum, and how these perceptions differ across ethnicity, place of qualification, and gender.

The results illustrate that staff at Gulf university in Oman demonstrate an understanding of some aspects of internationalization concerning the potential benefits they perceived in this non-Western context. The findings suggest that, according to participants' perceptions, the implementation of various aspects of internationalization (i.e. students, staff, and curriculum) in the Omani context is associated with benefits such as enhancing local students' and non-native staff members' English language skills, sharing experiences and cultural insights, and fostering cultural understandings. However, several tensions arose due to the university's lack of a formal internationalization policy and the very small number of international students enrolled.

5.1. Perceived vs. actual challenges of internationalization

To begin with, the staff appear to be uninformed about the actual challenges encountered when implementing internationalization. Although non-significant results were found for ethnicity, qualification, and gender (see Section 4.1), this may be due to the absence of international students in the ELCs at this university. The participants' positive perspectives and attitudes align with the potential benefits that both students and staff would gain in such a 'multinational' context (Knight, 2004; Leask, 2009).

However, based on the interviews, the findings suggest that the presence of international students in this Omani context would help local students improve their English language skills, enhance their motivation, and promote a deeper understanding of other cultures. The findings also suggest that challenges such as the limited socialization between local and international students and the tensions caused by the presence of international students (Harrison and Peacock, 2010; Sawir, 2011; Sawir et al., 2008) were either underestimated or not fully recognized. The limited awareness of actual challenges suggests a gap between perceived benefits and real challenges, indicating that staff views do not fully capture the realities of local and international student presence (see Gui et al., 2016; O'Reilly et al., 2010; Otten, 2003; Teekens, 2003).

5.2. One-way vs. mutual benefits of internationalization

This research has demonstrated that participants mainly perceive internationalization as a one-way benefit, in that they perceive internationalization in terms of benefiting the local context, rather than considering how staff can adapt their behaviour and their institutional culture and operations to align with the principles of internationalization that advocate mutual benefits. Interestingly, Section 4.2. shows no significant differences of ethnicity, qualification and gender, which aligns with the main growth phases of internationalization in many countries, such as South Korea (Lee and Bailey, 2020), China (Spencer-Oatey et al., 2017), and Denmark (Slethaug and Vinther, 2012), when increased (inbound) student mobility offers benefits (Rumbley and Altbach, 2016). However, based on the interviews, participants primarily highlighted the benefits for local students and staff. For example, the findings show that international students can help local students improve their cognitive skills, cultural understanding, motivation level, and English language, which all underscore the academic and social dimensions of internationalization. However, the benefits that international students can receive from local students were not recognized, which reflects the existing circumstances, in that there is a limited number of international students in this context. This challenges existing findings from other contexts observing mutual benefits between local and international students (Gui et al., 2016; O'Reilly et al., 2010; Shu et al., 2020), but more importantly, it indicates that mutuality (i.e. mutual benefits between local and international students) does not exist due to the absence of one of the parties. Therefore,

this study fills a gap in our knowledge in that this nuanced aspect is inevitably overlooked by staff in a context where there are few international students.

Additionally, the one-directional benefit was also evident when participants highlighted the advantages of having international staff. Firstly, Table 2 shows a significant difference between Arab and non-Arab staff members, with non-Arab participants yielding a higher mean rank. This finding challenges the principles of internationalization, which encourage the sharing of knowledge to equip staff with socially and culturally diverse perspectives (Knight, 2004). Second, the interviewees commented that international teachers share teaching experiences and techniques, but they did not mention what local teachers can offer international teachers in terms of teaching experiences, techniques, and cultural values. These findings underscore the potential shortcomings of mutual benefits between staff members, which were theoretically expected to result from the implementation of this activity (see Knight, 1997; Nguyen, 2018; Qiang, 2003). This is significant because it identifies a gap between the principles of internationalization, which promote mutual benefits and the reality on the ground (the actual one-way benefits perceived). Such evidence challenges the notion of achieving mutual benefits in internationalization, thereby contributing to the conceptual framework of internationalization.

5.3. Cultural barriers and local contextual challenges in implementing internationalization

Furthermore, this research has shown that whilst this university in Oman desires to join the global knowledge economy by implementing internationalization practices such as recruiting international staff members, curriculum internationalization, and establishing professional development programmes, it faces several cultural tensions which create challenges when implementing these activities. The findings illustrate that the university has attempted to equip teachers with 'international' textbooks, modern methodologies, and techniques to enhance their teaching and knowledge through professional development programmes and other academic events. Although this is key to successfully and effectively implementing internationalization activities (Knight, 2004), notable differences emerged mainly between Arab and non-Arab staff perspectives.

For example, regarding participation in international academic events such as conferences, Arab participants were less positive (see Table 3). This suggests there are cultural barriers, such as work culture (Al-Ghatrifi, 2016), to full integration into the global academic community. However, these differing perspectives could create conflict during the implementation of this internationalization initiative, potentially affecting the strategy's effectiveness at the university.

Moreover, differences arose regarding whether the textbooks should teach students about different cultures. A significant difference was found, with non-Arab participants yielding a higher mean rank (see Table 5). This finding suggests that Arab staff believe the textbooks in their ELCs do not adequately teach students about different cultures, indicating a lack of inclusivity or possibly including fewer topics related to Arab culture. Furthermore, there was a level of apprehension regarding the topics covered in the textbooks used in these ELCs, which were perceived as not being religiously appropriate for the Omani context. A significant difference was found between staff who completed their qualifications abroad versus domestically, as well as between male and female staff members (see Table 6). The higher mean rank was yielded by male participants and those with international qualifications. This finding suggests that education abroad exposes staff to different religious values, making them feel more open and less religiously sensitive (Erden, 2013; Karakaş, 2020). Additionally, Table 7 shows a significant difference between Arab and non-Arab participants regarding the importance of considering religious differences when designing a curriculum. Arab participants had a higher mean rank, suggesting that contextual factors influence their views, as Oman is a Muslim country. This indicates that there is an awareness of and sensitivity to religious issues among educators in this context (Al Sadi and Basit, 2013).

6. Conclusion and implications

This study examined academic staff perspectives on internationalization activities at a university in Oman, employing both qualitative and quantitative methods. The findings reveal that staff demonstrated a general understanding of internationalization and acknowledged the benefits of recruiting international students and staff, as well as incorporating an international curriculum. However, a significant gap emerged in the participants' awareness of the challenges associated with the presence of international students. As a conceptual contribution, addressing this gap in awareness through open communication and negotiation between staff and senior management will be crucial for the effective conceptualization and implementation of internationalization strategies and activities in this Omani context. In other words, ensuring that academic staff are proactively and continuously involved in strategic discussions will help bridge existing knowledge gaps, thereby enabling a more inclusive and effective implementation of internationalization initiatives.

Moreover, the study revealed that internationalization is predominantly viewed as a one-way benefit, with staff perceiving the presence of international students and staff as advantageous primarily to the local context. This reflects a common trend in contexts where international student populations are limited, such as Oman and Seychelles. To enhance the conceptual framework of internationalization, it is vital to address this one-way benefit perception. One potential solution is for staff to recognize the two-way benefits of internationalization.

Strategies that encourage cross-cultural exchange and knowledge sharing can help maximize the positive impacts of internationalization. Specifically, institutions should establish international mentorship programmes that pair local and international staff for collaborative knowledge exchange, fostering mutual learning and shared perspectives.

Finally, the findings highlighted cultural barriers and local contextual challenges that complicate the implementation of internationalization. By identifying these tensions, this study broadens our understanding of the ways in which internationalization is influenced by and intertwined with local socio-cultural contexts. This study contributes to the conceptualization of internationalization processes by illustrating how local cultural norms and perceptions can both enable and constrain internationalization efforts within the Arab HE context. This understanding fills a crucial gap for academics and policymakers seeking to internationalize education systems while remaining sensitive to local cultural and religious values.

A key practical implication of this study is the need to develop a targeted professional development framework that includes clear and explicit guidelines. Such a framework should offer flexible, context-sensitive training designed to bridge the gap between Arab and non-Arab staff perspectives and foster greater engagement in international academic activities. This would not only validate diverse cultural approaches but also encourage broader participation in the international academic community, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and inclusivity of internationalization initiatives.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of fostering a reciprocal approach to internationalization that acknowledges and appreciates local cultural and religious values. By implementing the suggested strategies, institutions outside the Western context can enhance cross-cultural understanding and promote a more inclusive and effective internationalization process.

Acknowledgements

Sincere gratitude is expressed to Professor Bruce Macfarlane, Dr. Robert Sharples, Professor Angeline Mbogo Barrett, Professor Gemma Derrick, and all the editors and reviewers, for their invaluable guidance, support, and feedback throughout this research. Additionally, appreciation is extended for the financial support provided by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation – Oman, and the University of Technology and Applied Sciences – Ibra, Oman.

References

- Abd Rashid, R.S.A. and Ibrahim, E.H.E. (2018). *English language textbooks and portrayal of culture: A content analysis*. MATEC Web of Conferences, 150, 5076. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201815005076>
- Al Abry, S. (2018). *Transnational Higher Education in Selected Private Colleges in Oman: Academic Staff Perceptions and Experiences*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Sheffield, UK. Available at: <http://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/21006/1/Salim%20thesis%20final%2011-7-2018%20%281%29.pdf>
- Al Harthy, M.A.M. (2011). *Private higher education in the Sultanate of Oman: Rationales, development and challenges*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Kassel, Germany. Available at: <https://kobra.uni-kassel.de/bitstream/handle/123456789/2011062237904/ThesisMasoudAlHarthy.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y>
- Al Sadi, F.H., and Basit, T.N. (2013). 'Religious tolerance in oman: Addressing religious prejudice through educational intervention'. *British Educational Research Journal*, 39 (3), pp.447-472. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411926.2011.652071>
- Al'Abri, K.M., Al-Naabi, I.S. and Ambusaidi, A.K. (2022). 'Are schools in Oman planning to produce global citizens? A critical analysis of schools' visions and missions'. *Citizenship, Social and Economics Education*, 21 (2), pp.118-135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14788047221086562>
- Albusaidi, S.S. (2022a). 'Investigating Internationalization at Home: A Case Study of Academic Staff Perspectives in a Local College in Oman'. In E. Meletiadiou (ed.), *Handbook of Research on Practices for Advancing Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education*, pp.104-124, IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9628-9.ch006>
- Albusaidi, S.S. (2022b). 'Measuring the Quality of Higher Education Internationalization in Oman'. In C. Msengi, G. Larney and K. Spratt (eds.), *Contemporary Issues in Multicultural and Global Education*, pp.240-264. IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-7404-1.ch013>
- Albusaidi, S.S. (2024). *Exploring academic staff perspectives on the internationalization of higher education in Oman: A mixed methods study*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Bristol. <https://research-information.bris.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/exploring-academic-staff-perspectives-on-the-internationalization>
- Al-Ghatrifi, Y. (2016). *The professional development of teachers in Higher Education in Oman: a case study of English teachers in the Colleges of Applied Sciences*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Reading, UK. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/reader/42155240>
- Al-Issa, A.S. and Al-Bulushi, A.H. (2012). 'English language teaching reform in sultanate of Oman: The case of theory and practice disparity'. *Educational Research for Policy and Practice*, 11 (2), pp.141-176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10671-011-9110-0>
- Al-Lamki, S.M. (2006). 'The Development of Private Higher Education in the Sultanate of Oman: Perception and Analysis'. *International Journal of Private Education*, 1 (1), pp.54-77.
- Altbach, P.G. (2013). *The international imperative in higher education* (1st ed.). Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Altbach, P.G. and Knight, J. (2007). 'The internationalization of higher education: Motivations and realities'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11 (3-4), pp.290-305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315307303542>
- Behrnd, V. and Porzelt, S. (2012). 'Intercultural competence and training outcomes of students with experiences abroad'. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 36 (2), pp.213-223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2011.04.005>
- Benet-Martínez, V., Lee, F. and Leu, J. (2006). 'Biculturalism and cognitive complexity: Expertise in cultural representations'. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 37 (4), pp.386-407. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022106288476>

- Carli, L.L. (1990). 'Gender, language, and influence'. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 59 (5), pp.941-951. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.59.5.941>
- Carli, L.L. (2009). 'Gender and group behavior'. In J.C. Chrisler and D.R. McCreary (eds.), *Handbook of gender research in psychology*, pp.337-358. Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1467-5_14
- Cheng, K.K.Y. and Beigi, A.B. (2012). 'Education and religion in Iran: The inclusiveness of EFL (English as a foreign language) textbooks'. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 32 (2), pp.310-315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2011.05.006>
- de Wit, H. (2002). *Internationalization of higher education in the United States of America and Europe: A historical, comparative and conceptual analysis*. Westport, CT: Greenwood.
- Erden, Ö. (2013). *An assessment of MoNE-YLYS scholarship program from the perspectives of scholars': Changes in cultural, political, economic and educational perceptions*. Master's Thesis, Middle East Technical University, Turkey. Available at: <https://open.metu.edu.tr/bitstream/handle/11511/22721/index.pdf>
- Gong, Y., Gao, X., Li, M. and Lai, C. (2021). 'Cultural adaptation challenges and strategies during study abroad: New Zealand students in China'. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 34 (4), pp.417-437. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2020.1856129>
- Gui, Y., Safdar, S. and Berry, J. (2016). 'Mutual intercultural relations among university students in Canada'. *Frontiers (Boston, Mass.): The Interdisciplinary Journal of Study Abroad*, 27 (1), pp.17-32. <https://doi.org/10.36366/frontiers.v27i1.372>
- Hamidaddin, A. (2019). *Tweeted heresies: Saudi Islam in transformation*. Oxford University Press.
- Hardy, D. (2021). 'All at Sea: Small Island Universities in the Indian Ocean'. *Seychelles Research Journal*, 3 (2). Retrieved from: https://seychellesresearchjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/all_at_sea-small_island_universities_in_the_indian_ocean-dennis_hardy-srj-3-2.pdf
- Harrison, N. and Peacock, N. (2010). 'Cultural distance, mindfulness and passive xenophobia: Using integrated threat theory to explore home higher education students' perspectives on 'internationalization at home''. *British Educational Research Journal*, 36 (6), pp.877-902. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920903191047>
- Heng, T.T. (2017). 'Voices of Chinese international students in USA colleges: 'I want to tell them that...'' *Studies in Higher Education*, 42 (5), pp.833-850. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2017.1293873>
- Hubais, A. and Muftahu, M. (2022). 'Internationalization of curriculum in Omani higher education: Perceptions of academic staff in UTAS'. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 11 (5), p.134. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v11n5p134>
- Jeannin, L.M. (2016). *Professional Development Needs of Faculty Members in an International University in Thailand*. Walden University. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/2187/>
- Jones, E. (2017). 'Problematising and reimagining the notion of 'international student experience''. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42 (5), pp.933-943. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2017.1293880>
- Jones, E. and Killick, D. (2007). 'Internationalisation of the curriculum'. In E. Jones, and S. Brown (eds.), *Internationalising Higher Education*, pp.109-119. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.
- Karakaş, A. (2020). 'Disciplining transnationality? the impact of study abroad educational experiences on Turkish returnee scholars' lives, careers and identity'. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 15 (3), pp.252-272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745499920946223>
- Kaushik, V. and Walsh, C.A. (2019). 'Pragmatism as a research paradigm and its implications for social work research'. *Social Sciences (Basel)*, 8 (9), pp.255-272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8090255>
- Knight, J. and de Wit, H. (1995). 'Strategies for internationalisation of higher education: Historical and conceptual perspectives'. In H. de Wit (ed.), *Strategies for internationalisation of higher education: a comparative study of Australia, Canada, Europe and the United States of America*, pp.5-33. Amsterdam: European Association for International Education (EAIE).

- Knight, J. (1997). 'Internationalization of Higher Education: a conceptual framework'. In J. Knight and H. de Wit (eds.), *Internationalisation of Higher Education in Asia Pacific Countries*, pp.5-19. Amsterdam: European Association for International Education.
- Knight, J. (1999). 'Internationalisation of Higher Education'. In J. Knight, and H. de Wit, (eds.). *Quality and internationalisation in higher education*, pp.13-28. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- Knight, J. (2004). 'Internationalisation remodeled: Definition, approaches, and rationales'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 8 (1), pp.5-31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315303260832>
- Knight, J. (2013). The changing landscape of higher education internationalisation – for better or worse?' *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 17 (3), pp.84-90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2012.753957>
- Kufaine, N. (2024). 'Understanding Characteristics of Definitions for Internationalisation of Higher Education: Concept Analysis'. *Creative Education*, 15 (6), pp.1029-1042.
- Leask, B. (2001). 'Internationalisation: Changing contexts and their implications for teaching, learning and assessment'. In L. Richardson and J. Lidstone (eds.), *Flexible Learning for a Flexible Society*, pp.389-401. Proceedings of ASET-HERDSA 2000 Conference, Toowoomba, Qld, 2-5 July 2000. ASET and HERDSA. <http://www.aset.org.au/confs/aset-herdsa2000/procs/leask1.html>
- Leask, B. (2004). 'Internationalisation outcomes for all students using information and communication technologies (ICTs)'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 8 (4), pp.336-351. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315303261778>
- Leask, B. (2009). 'Using formal and informal curricula to improve interactions between home and international students'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 13 (2), pp.205-221. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315308329786>
- LeBeau, L.G. (2018). 'A Process Approach to Internationalization – Utilizing De Wit's Internationalization Circle (Modified Version) for Internationalization Planning'. *International Research and Review*, 7 (2), pp.1-17.
- Lee, A.R. and Bailey, D.R. (2020). 'Examining South Korean University Students' Interactions with International Students'. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16 (3), pp.43-58. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v16i3.8622>
- Luxon, T. and Peelo, M. (2009). 'Internationalization: Its implications for curriculum design and course development in UK higher education'. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 46 (1), pp.51-60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703290802646172>
- Marangell, S., Arkoudis, S. and Baik, C. (2018). 'Developing a host culture for international students: What does it take'. *Journal of International Students*, 8 (3), pp.1440-1458.
- Marginson, S. (2014). 'Student self-formation in international education'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 18 (1), pp.6-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315313513036>
- McDermott-Levy, R. (2011). 'Going alone: The lived experience of female Arab-Muslim nursing students living and studying in the United States'. *Nursing Outlook*, 59 (5), pp.266-277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2011.02.006>
- Mok, K.H. (2007). 'Questing for internationalization of universities in Asia: Critical reflections'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11 (3-4), pp.433-454. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306291945>
- Muhamad, R. (2009). 'Religiosity, ethical judgments and Malaysian Muslim students'. *Journal of Business Systems, Governance and Ethics*, 4 (1), pp.55-66. <https://doi.org/10.15209/jbsge.v4i1.154>
- Nguyen, T.P.T. (2018). *The internationalisation of higher education in Vietnamese universities*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Portsmouth, UK. Available at: https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/portal/files/12991052/Nguyen_PhD_Final_Thesis_.pdf

- O'Reilly, A., Ryan, D. and Hickey, T. (2010). 'The psychological well-being and sociocultural adaptation of short-term international students in Ireland'. *Journal of College Student Development*, 51 (5), pp.584-598. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2010.0011>
- Otten, M. (2003). 'Intercultural learning and diversity in higher education'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 7 (1), pp.12-26. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315302250177>
- Patil-Vishwanath, T. and Mummery, J. (2019). 'Reflecting critically on the critical disposition within internationalisation of the curriculum (IoC): The developmental journey of a curriculum design team'. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 38 (2), pp.354-368. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2018.1515181>
- Qiang, Z. (2003). 'Internationalization of higher education: Towards a conceptual framework'. *Policy Futures in Education*, 1 (2), pp.248-270. <https://doi.org/10.2304/pfie.2003.1.2.5>
- Ramadan, I. (2017). *Experiences of Muslim academics in UK Higher Education Institutions*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Edinburgh, UK. Available at: <https://era.ed.ac.uk/handle/1842/31350>
- Rumbley, L.E. and Altbach, P.G. (2016). 'The local and the global in higher education internationalization'. In E. Jones, R. Coelen, J. Beelen and H. de Wit (eds.), *Global and local internationalisation*, pp.7-13. Sense Publishers.
- Saunders, M. and Fisher, R. (2020). 'Some experiences of non-EU international students following an access to higher education diploma course in a general further education college in the north of England'. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 25 (4), pp.480-500. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2020.1846317>
- Sawir, E. (2011). 'Academic staff response to international students and internationalising the curriculum: The impact of disciplinary differences'. *The International Journal for Academic Development*, 16 (1), pp.45-57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2011.546224>
- Sawir, E., Marginson, S., Deumert, A., Nyland, C. and Ramia, G. (2008). 'Loneliness and international students: An Australian study'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 12 (2), pp.148-180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315307299699>
- Seeber, M., Cattaneo, M., Huisman, J. and Paleari, S. (2016). 'Why do higher education institutions internationalize? an investigation of the multilevel determinants of internationalization rationales'. *Higher Education*, 72 (5), pp.685-702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-015-9971-x>
- Shu, F., Ahmed, S.F., Pickett, M.L., Ayman, R. and McAbee, S.T. (2020). 'Social support perceptions, network characteristics, and international student adjustment'. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 74, pp.136-148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2019.11.002>
- Singh, J.K. (2019). 'Evidence and benefits of postgraduate international students-staff members partnership in extra-curricular activities: A Malaysian perspective'. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 38 (7), pp.1475-1488. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2018.1436527>
- Slethaug, G. and Vinther, J. (2012). 'The challenges of multilingualism for international students in Denmark'. In J. Ryan (ed.), *Cross-Cultural Teaching and Learning for Home and International Students*, pp.96-108. Routledge.
- Spencer-Oatey, H., Dauber, D., Jing, J. and Lifei, W. (2017). 'Chinese students' social integration into the university community: Hearing the students' voices'. *Higher Education*, 74 (5), pp.739-756. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0074-0>
- Subedi, D. (2016). 'Explanatory sequential mixed method design as the third research community of knowledge claim'. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4 (7), pp.570-577.
- Sung, C.C.M. (2019). 'Investments and identities across contexts: A case study of a Hong Kong undergraduate student's L2 learning experiences'. *Journal of Language, Identity, and Education*, 18 (3), pp.190-203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2018.1552149>

- Svetlik, I. and Braček-Lalić, A. (2016). 'The impact of the internationalization of higher education on academic staff development – the case of Slovenian public universities'. *Studies in Higher Education*, 41 (2), pp.364-380. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2014.942266>
- Sysoyev, P.V. (ed.). (2002). *Identity, culture, and language teaching*. CREES, Center for Russian, East European and Eurasian Studies, University of Iowa.
- Teekens, H. (2003). 'The requirement to develop specific skills for teaching in an intercultural setting'. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 7 (1), pp.108-119. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315302250192>
- Undie, D.A., Etim, E.E. and Samuel, H.S. (2025). 'Promoting Diversity and Inclusion in Internationalization Initiatives: Challenges and Best Practices'. In *International Academic Transformations and Cross-Border Collaborations*, pp.129-144. IGI Global Scientific Publishing.
- Wang, F., Clarke, A. and Webb, A.S. (2019). 'Tailored for China: Did it work? Reflections on an intensive study abroad programme for Chinese student teachers'. *Teachers and Teaching, Theory and Practice*, 25 (7), pp.800-820. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2019.1676224>
- Wang, M. (2018). 'Contextualizing internationalization in higher education: Study abroad programs for global human resource development'. In E. Stigger, M. Wang, D. Laurence, A. Bordilovskaya and M. Wang (eds.), *Internationalization within Higher Education: Perspectives from Japan*, pp.37-55. Singapore: Springer.
- Woodhead, L. (2012). 'Gender differences in religious practice and significance'. *Travail, Genre Et Sociétés*, 27 (1), pp.33-54. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.027.0033>
- Yuden, Y., Chuki, S. and Dorji, T. (2020). 'Gender sensitivity in pedagogical practices in secondary education in Bhutan'. *Research in Educational Policy and Management*, 2 (2), pp.38-51. <https://doi.org/10.46303/repam.2020.3>

Saud Albusaidi is an English language lecturer at the University of Technology and Applied Sciences in Oman. He has been a lecturer in higher education since 2013. Saud holds a Doctorate in Education (Ed.D.) from the University of Bristol, UK, and an MA in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) from the University of Huddersfield, UK. Saud has published several articles and book chapters on topics related to higher education. His research interests include the internationalization of higher education, curriculum development, and internationalization at home.

saud.s.albusaidi@utas.edu.om

Aaisha Albusaidi is an English language instructor at A'Sharqiyah University in Oman. She has been in higher education since 2018. She has an MA in TESOL from the University of Huddersfield, UK. Aaisha is interested in globalization and internationalization. She is also interested in technology and AI tools and how they impact learning and teaching in ESL contexts.

aaisha.albusaidi@asu.edu.om

Appendix 1: Interview Questions

1. What does it mean for a university to be ‘international’?
2. What activities or aspects do you think make a university ‘international’?
 - a. What are the advantages/disadvantages of these activities?
3. Are you familiar with the term ‘internationalization’? What does it mean to you?
4. How do you see ‘internationalization’ in terms of: (How has internationalization impacted these?) staff, students, the curriculum
5. Do you think it is a good idea or not for your university to be ‘internationalized’ (or employ such ‘internationalization’ aspects)?
6. Do you think your university should further support ‘internationalizing’ its activities and practices? If yes, why?/ if no, why not?
7. What are the motivations behind adopting these ‘internationalization’ activities/practices?
8. How does ‘internationalization’ affect your daily work activities?
9. What are the benefits of ‘internationalizing’ this university?
10. What are the risks of ‘internationalizing’ this university?
11. Do you have any further comments/suggestions/recommendations regarding the ‘internationalization’ of this university?